

PEDAGOGICAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF ACHIEVING QUALITY EFFECTIVENESS IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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One of the main tasks of today's education system is to teach foreign languages to the young generation by introducing modern pedagogic and information communication technologies, and to fundamentally improve the system of training specialists who can speak these languages fluently. Since ancient times, people have had a desire to learn foreign languages. Learning foreign languages in primary grades is not only the acquisition and acquisition of information about the language, but also the process of the student engaging in active communication. In order to communicate in a foreign language, students need to acquire the vocabulary of that language. In the language word wealth without occupying standing and listening understand or speak can Language learning personality in society go to sleep important questions is considered Hi there the means is death the language natural in mu h it in the family, community between or organized without education in institutions take over can Language to events about knowledge while theoretical in terms of is taught. X, a lkaro relationships the climax received in our time languages Knowledge of multilingualism huge importance occupation is enough Start drinking from class foreign the language child's opportunity to learn and ability how from being katy look is useful because foreign language of the child to know processes i - memory, attention, thinking, imagination and of perception development positive effect shows Teaching style of methodology important from issues is one The methodology is foreign languages teaching style karab method and principles work chi q adi Science teaching style in defining basically two common demand and their to each other the fact that in mind catch necessary;

- 1) Selected teaching style through burnt to the goal reach or reach not get demand
- 2) Selected teaching style students by appropriation or master not get demand

Foreign today language teaching in the methodology science teaching style the following including q amrab takes

1. Language materials i - phonetics, grammar, vocabulary, orthography
2. Skills - pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar
3. K skills -listening understanding, speaking, teaching, writing, translation to do
4. Information sources i - speech theme, texts, language concept.

A properly chosen teaching method is the main factor in achieving the goal. When choosing a method, first of all, the purpose of teaching is taken into account. Each teacher has his own teaching style. In order to increase the activity of students, various non-traditional methods, use of technical means, introduction of contests are widely used during training. The quality of education is related to the student's ability to effectively engage in independent reading aimed at mastering the educational content, to think independently and think. Pedagogical technology has been interpreted differently in different periods. In particular, the use of audio-visual equipment, teaching with the help of equipment, programmed education, planned education were understood in the educational process. Currently, pedagogical technology; - the use of computer and information technologies in the educational process, - the educational process consists of organizational tools;; - a unique scientific-based innovative

approach to teaching; - the scientific and methodological basis of the organization of the process that guarantees the formation of a complete person; it is considered a process that guarantees teaching to think freely. In the process of educational technology, under the guidance of the teacher, the student gets independent knowledge, learns and assimilates. The main process of pedagogical technology includes organization, cooperation, improvement, analysis, comparison, generalization, conclusion, management, control, evaluation, etc. The main characteristics of pedagogical technology;

1.. The student is not taught, but taught to study independently. For this purpose, the student is taught to analyze the learning material independently, to think, to think creatively, and to come to personal conclusions.

2.. The student is not given ready-made knowledge, he is taught to acquire knowledge independently from its sources. In this, the student is taught to strengthen and expand what the teacher taught in the lesson by teaching the student to use the textbook first, and then to independently use additional literature and encyclopedias.

3.. It is guaranteed that all students will learn at the level of their abilities. In this case, the student's mastery is determined by the level of skills and qualifications to be able to use the knowledge he has learned in life and in his practical activities.

4.. If all teachers learn the mechanism of pedtechnology, they will achieve almost the same result in education, especially the use of pedagogical technology in training is considered the most acceptable educational method in teaching foreign languages among all subjects. The main conditions for applying educational technologies to the educational process are as follows; - the main conditions of application in the process of teaching a foreign language are the following - development of free communication of each student in the process of learning a foreign language , - the use of methods and modern educational tools that increase the activity of the learner in the educational process and also in the course of the lesson. It is known that innovative technologies are the introduction of innovations and changes to the pedagogical process and teacher's and student's activities, and interactive methods are used in its implementation. The uniqueness of these methods is that they are implemented only through the joint activity of the teacher and students. This process of pedagogic cooperation has its own characteristics, it ensures that the student is not indifferent during the lesson, thinks independently, is involved in creativity and research, ensures the continuity of his interest in science during the educational process, and ensures the continuous organization of the cooperative activities of the teacher and students.

Pedagogical technology in the educational process is an integral process in a clear sequence, which is aimed at providing a carefully designed and guaranteed result based on the student's curiosity and curiosity. During the preparation for the lesson, the teacher selects educational tools according to the topic of the lesson and focuses on the used methods and educational tools. The teacher will be able to achieve the intended goal only if he can use the new methods and technical tools appropriate for each subject. This directs the students to independent learning, to think about a specific topic and to be creatively active. Today, the widely used methods are "Four-part", "Brainstorming", "Working in small groups", "Role play", "Working game", "Problem situation", "Circle interview", "Discussion", "Project ", "Directive mant", "Cluster" methods, teachers achieve effective results. In addition to the interactive methods listed above, the use of the "Chain" method, "Akl Khakhi", "Memory exercise" is very suitable

for the purpose of teaching foreign languages . during topic on the surface come out problems innovative technologies apply through easy the solution to find can Teacher of students in class activities sure one to the goal direction , har one lesson training thorough planning , modern pedagogical technologies based on organize to be done must If so , it is new exercise samples choose addition training as to the plan introduction , lesson intergroup competition in spirit take to go finally effective And here telling win necessarily , the student's each one the answer own on time ra g' by beating to go need Teacher constant respectively students to the learned foreign language belongs to topic on the surface thought to report urge, suggestion mulo h azarin, talent demonstration to do has been attempts by hand b - q uvvatseh, of this for conditions and chance by creating to give should.

References:

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